

THE IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS ON THE
QUALITY OF PUMPKIN FRUITS DURING STORAGE

Umidov Shavkat Ergashevich, Doctor philosophy of agricultural science (PhD),
Tashkent state agrarian university, Tashkent, e-mail: umidov_shavkat@mail.ru

Genjebekov Marat Sovetovich – Doctoral student of Karakalpakstan Institute of
Agriculture and Agrotechnologies

Annotation. This research explores how various technological properties affect the quality of pumpkin fruits throughout the storage process. By examining key factors such as moisture content, ripeness, and handling methods, the study aims to understand their role in maintaining or altering the fruit's quality over time. The investigation highlights the importance of proper storage conditions in preserving the pumpkins' freshness, texture, and nutritional value, ultimately contributing to improved post-harvest management practices..

Keywords: Pumpkin, pulp thickness, weight, consistency, degree of tenderness, technological indicators.

Significant advancements have been made globally in the processing of pumpkin fruits. These studies primarily focus on areas such as pectin secretion in pumpkins, oil extraction from pumpkin seeds, and the examination of pumpkin's pharmacological properties. Notably, European countries and China have widely adopted technologies for extracting pumpkin seed oil. However, in these regions, there has been less focus on the agrobiological and technological characteristics of juicy squash varieties, their storage, and juice production technologies. In Uzbekistan, pumpkin cultivation and consumption are not as prevalent as other vegetables. However, regional varieties of pumpkin are being produced and sold across various parts of the country, meeting local demand. There is limited knowledge about the market potential and nutritional value of different squash types grown in various regions, as well as the specific storage conditions and processing methods for each variety.

The results for a detailed study of the factors affecting the quality variability of pumpkin fruits are based on a comprehensive indicator of quality, which also expresses the specific characteristics of each variety as a percentage. By using this method to analyze the quality of pumpkin varieties, it is possible to identify which indicators remain stable throughout the life cycle of a particular variety and which are subject to change.

Pumpkin fruits are commonly used both in their fresh form and for processing. A large portion of the harvest is used for producing canned goods on an industrial scale. For the processing industry, the weight of the pumpkin fruit, the proportion of flesh, and its thickness are important, especially when consumed fresh. These indicators are also key to the technological properties of pumpkin fruits.

The technological properties of pumpkins are influenced by the structure of their fruit. A pumpkin fruit is a multi-seeded pseudo-fruit, consisting of the rind, flesh, and seeds, with a placenta and a cavity filled with seeds. The parenchyma above the placenta forms the flesh of the fruit. Studies have shown that the composition of pumpkin fruit includes 17% rind, 73% flesh, and 10% seeds, with these proportions varying depending on the species and variety of pumpkin.

Table 1.

Technological composition of pumpkin fruits studied (2023-2024)

Variety name	Fruit mass, kg	The amount of flesh, %	Flesh thickness, cm	Level of flesh, LF
Ispanskaya 73	8,20	77,18	5,0-6,0	0,73
Michurinskaya Sladkaya 13	3,50	71,33	2,5	0,68
Volzhskaya Seraya 92	13,5	77,26	5,0	0,72
Rossiyanka	4,80	74,05	5,5	0,66
Medovaya	3,45	72,65	3,5-4,5	0,65
Stofuntovaya	10,7	74,69	3,5-4,5	0,68
Non kadi	6,20	77,45	4,0	0,68
Shirintoy	5,32	74,15	3,5-4,0	0,64
Biryuchekutskaya 27	4,80	74,18	3,0-3,5	0,64
Kustovaya oranjevaya	2,93	68,91	2,0-3,0	0,61
Mozoleevskaya	7,59	74,27	5,0-6,5	0,66
Vegetable Spaghetti	1,50	70,02	2,0	0,62
Palov Kadu 268	6,30	78,45	4,0	0,73
Kashgarskaya 1644	4,72	74,15	3,5-4,0	0,66
Korean Pumpkin	2,80	74,18	3,0-3,5	0,64
Vitaminaya	3,93	68,91	3,0-3,5	0,61
Gapvu tradiny (Корея)	4,20	74,27	5,0-6,5	0,68

The data presented in the table provides detailed insights into the technological composition of various pumpkin varieties, including their fruit mass, flesh content, flesh thickness, and flesh quality level. These factors play a crucial role in determining the suitability of each pumpkin variety for different processing methods and consumption purposes.

The weight of the pumpkins varies significantly across different varieties, with the smallest being **Vegetable Spaghetti** at 1.5 kg, and the largest being **Volzhskaya Seraya 92** at 13.5 kg. The average fruit mass for the varieties listed is approximately 5.56 kg. This wide range indicates that some varieties are more suitable for large-scale industrial processing, while others might be better for smaller, niche markets or direct consumption. Larger pumpkins like **Volzhskaya Seraya 92** are likely to be more valuable for products such as canned pumpkin or puree, where high yield is important. On the other hand, smaller varieties such as **Vegetable Spaghetti** might be better suited for specialized uses, such as fresh market sales or gourmet products.

In terms of flesh content, the percentage varies from **68.91%** for **Kustovaya oranjevaya**

to **78.45%** for **Palov Kadu 268**, with the average being **73.89%**. Flesh content is a vital factor in determining how much of the pumpkin can be used for processing or consumption. Higher flesh content generally indicates better yield for products like pumpkin puree, canned pumpkin, and pumpkin-based soups or sauces. Varieties like **Palov Kadu 268**, with higher flesh content, are particularly valuable for such industrial processes, as they would provide more usable product per unit of weight.

Flesh thickness is another important characteristic, with values ranging from **2.0 cm** (for **Kustovaya oranjevaya** and **Vegetable Spaghetti**) to **5.0-6.5 cm** (for varieties like **Volzhskaya Seraya 92** and **Mozoleevskaya**). Thicker flesh generally indicates better texture and a higher yield, making these varieties more desirable for both processing and fresh consumption. Thicker-fleshed pumpkins are often preferred for making products like pumpkin puree or canned pumpkin, where texture and consistency are essential.

The level of flesh quality, denoted as LF, is another key indicator of a pumpkin's overall processing quality. This value ranges from **0.61** (for **Kustovaya oranjevaya** and **Vitaminnaya**) to **0.73** (for **Ispanskaya 73** and **Palov Kadu 268**), with an average of **0.66**. A higher LF suggests better texture, flavor, and suitability for processing. Pumpkins with higher LF values are likely to produce higher-quality end products, whether they are consumed fresh or processed into items like juice, puree, or canned goods.

When considering which pumpkin varieties are best suited for various purposes, it is essential to balance all these factors. For example, **Volzhskaya Seraya 92** stands out with its large fruit mass, high flesh percentage, and thick flesh, making it a prime candidate for large-scale processing. Its high flesh content and size are ideal for producing canned products or puree. Similarly, **Palov Kadu 268** offers high flesh content and good quality flesh, making it suitable for both fresh consumption and industrial processing.

On the other hand, smaller varieties like **Vegetable Spaghetti** and **Kustovaya oranjevaya** might be better suited for fresh market sales or specialized uses, as their smaller size and lower flesh content make them less ideal for large-scale processing but potentially more attractive for niche markets or gourmet products. Additionally, the relatively thinner flesh of these varieties may make them less suitable for certain types of processing, such as puree production, where texture is a key consideration.

Overall, the data highlights the significant diversity in pumpkin varieties, with different characteristics making each variety more suitable for specific applications. By understanding the technological composition of these pumpkins, producers can better match varieties to their processing needs, whether for fresh consumption, long-term storage, or industrial-scale products like puree, canned goods, or juice. This comprehensive analysis allows for a more efficient approach to pumpkin cultivation and processing, ensuring that each variety is used in the most optimal way possible.

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